

ИМАМ БУХАРИ LIFE CREATION

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Annotation: In the third century, which was a golden age in the development of the science of hadith's great achievements were made in the study of hadith's. For example, the authors of six authentic collections of hadith's, which are recognized as the most authoritative sources in the entire Islamic world, have lived and worked. Among them, Imam al-Bukhari, who was awarded the honorary title of "Amir al-Mu'minin in the science of hadith's," is a great scholar of special note. This article discusses the life and work of Imam al-Bukhari.

Keywords: Imam-Bukhari, creation, hadith's, Islam, scholars, students, period, heritage.

His full name was Abu-Abdullah Muhammad ibn-Isma'il ibn-Ibrahim ibn al-Mughirah ibn-Bardazbeh al-Juafi al-Bukhari, and he was born on the 13th of Shaw'al 194 AH in the city of Bukhara. Unlike many other scholars, al-Bukhari's date of birth is accurate because his father, Isma'il, was a scholar of his time, and the paper on which he wrote his son's birthday in his own handwriting was made available to contemporary scholars, and there is no doubt about its accuracy. Al-Bukhari died at a young age when his father died and he was raised by his mother. From an early age, he was intelligent, sharp-witted, and passionate about enlightenment, and studied various sciences, especially hadith's, with great interest. Sources say that from the age of ten, he read and memorized hadith's he had heard from various narrators in his country, as well as hadith's collections from scholars such as Abdull'ah-ibn al-Mubarak and Waq'i, and engaged in heated debates with his teacher, Sheikh-Dahili. In 825, sixteen-year-old al-Bukhari traveled to Hij'az with his mother and brother Ahmad, visiting the holy cities of Mecca and Medina, living in Hij'az for six years, and furthering his knowledge of hadith's. He lived in cities such as Basra, Kuf'a, and Baghdad, where he studied hadith's with well-known scholars, as well as jurisprudence, participated in scientific debates with great scholars, and taught science.

Most of Imam al-Bukhari's life was spent in exile. He said: "I went to Egypt, Damascus, Mesopotamia twice and to Basra four times. I lived in Hij'az for six years and I don't know how many times I went to Baghdad and Kuf'a". Both during his travels and while living in a city, he worked tirelessly to improve his

knowledge and to translate the hadith's he had collected. According to the author, while living in Baghdad, he often wrote in the moonlight and wrote books by candlelight on dark nights. Al-Bukhari studied with many scholars in order to increase his knowledge. According to al-Hakim of Nishap'ur, the number of teachers was about ninety, and they were known as Muhammad ibn-Yus'uf al-Gharabi, Ubaydull'ah ibn-Musa al-Abasi, Abu-Bakr Abdull'ah-ibn az-Zubayr al-Hamidi ibn-Rahav'ih. Imam Ishaq-ibn Ibrahim, Imam Ahmad ibn-Hanb'al, Ali-ibn al-Madani and others. Al-Bukhari, in turn, mentored many of his students. His students are Ishaq-ibn Muhammad ar-Ramadi, Abdull'ah ibn-Muhammad al-Masnadi, Muhammad i bn Khal'af ibn-Qutayba, Ibrahim al-Harbi, Abu-Isa at-Termizi, Muhammad ibn-Nasr al-Marwazi, Muslim-ibn al-Hajjaj.

Imam al-Bukhari was not only a great scholar, but also distinguished by his good character, humanity, kindness, generosity and incomparable generosity. He is also known for his sharp wit and strong memory. Sources say that al-Bukhari memorized about 600,000 hadith's. After returning from abroad, Imam al-Bukhari taught hadith's to many students and scholars in his native Bukhara. Many respected him, but some jealous, malicious people could not see al-Bukhari. As a result, al-Bukhari's relationship with the Emir of Bukhara, Khalid ibn-Ahmad az-Zuhali, was severed due to jealousy. The reason for this was that the Amir asked the scholar to come to him and read the books Al-Jame 'as-Sahih and At-Tarikh. But al-Bukhari said, "I do not despise science and take it to the gates of the rulers. Whoever needs knowledge, let him seek it". But Allah will forgive me on the Day of Judgment for not hiding knowledge and spending it on the Talib'an. The Emir did not like the answer and ordered al-Bukhari to leave the city. Al-Bukhari then traveled to Samarkand, where he lived with his students and relatives for some time. He became seriously ill and died at the age of 60 in 256 AH.

Imam al-Bukhari left a rich and valuable scientific legacy for generations, and he wrote more than twenty works. Undoubtedly, the most important work of the great scholar is Al-Jame' as-Sahih. This work is also known as-Sahih al-Bukhari. The most important aspect of this is that the hadith's scholars before Imam al-Bukhari did not select all the hadith's they heard in their collections. Imam al-Bukhari, on the other hand, divided the hadith's he had heard from the various narrators into sections, separated their trustworthy ones, and created a separate book. According to All'ama ibn-Salah, the number of authentic hadith's included in al-Bukhari's work is 7,275, including 4,000 hadith's, and 4,000 hadith's without repetition.

In short, The hadith's included in Imam al-Bukhari's collections are a set of true human qualities and exemplary practices, such as love, generosity, openness, respect for parents, women and adults, kindness to orphans, compassion for the poor, love for the motherland, diligence and honesty. It contains instructions, advice and counsel on what is good, what is bad, what to do, what to refrain from, which are of great educational importance for the people of our modern society, especially for the younger generation.

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